

TRANSFORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL NEEDS OF RUSSIAN SCHOOL TEACHERS AND HEADMASTERS IN POST COVID ERA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8055476>

Abstract. *The article analyses the results of the survey conducted among teachers and heads of educational organizations in Russia. The main tasks that continuing education can solve, on the part of teachers, were indicated as the following: "to increase the efficiency of work" and "to improve the quality of education". On the part of heads of educational organizations in relation to teachers, the following were chosen as the main tasks: "ensuring the quality of education" and "professional development of school teachers". The authors suggest the following solutions to these challenges: adjustment of marketing and communication strategies of providers of additional education services, organization of personalized training.*

The data presented in this article will be interesting for the managers of educational organizations, employees of educational authorities of all levels, specialists in teacher training and school managers.

Keywords: *continuing professional education, teachers, heads of educational institutions, educational needs, continuing education hub, personalized training, professional competencies, professional development of teachers and school leaders.*

Introduction

Continuing education in Russia is an actively developing sphere, but for the most part the decision to obtain additional competences is left to the employees themselves [14]. Nevertheless, there are spheres in Russia where continuing education is regulated by the state, such as pedagogy.

Thus, the minimum frequency of obtaining continuing professional education in the profile of pedagogical activity is at least once every three years with the duration of at least sixteen hours, but changes in education, emergence of new normative acts regulating professional and educational activity, emergence of new technologies, techniques, teaching methods, appearance of professional standards and new digital technologies become quite a frequent reason for the lack of professional competences of educators to fully develop in new conditions.

The need for continuing education in the field of pedagogy is growing, and the market, in which both public and private organizations are involved, is trying to respond as quickly as possible to the emergence of new directions and meet the demand. However, quite often the lack of awareness of the true needs of teachers in the field of continuing education is a problem.

Research work in the field of the needs in continuing education is carried out in many regions, but most often it concerns the conceptual and systemic aspects of additional education or

the formation of specific competencies [1,2,5,6,11]. There is another limitation: most of the works devoted to the study of continuing education for teachers in Russia do not distinguish between a teacher and managerial staff of educational organizations, although each employee has its own specifics. Most often, heads and deputy heads of educational organizations are studied separately, taking into account special competencies that management personnel need to have, taking into account the specifics of regulatory and state regulation of education [9].

A separate issue is the change in consumer demand, given the widespread transition to full distance learning, which has occurred in the context of the 2020 pandemic. Although the digitalization of education and the development of digital skills of teachers and administrators have been talked about for quite some time, practice has nevertheless shown a very low level of digital competence, which has had to be studied at a forced pace. In a study by the Yandex team, including digital competences of teachers, the dependence of the age of the teacher on the level of digital competence is very well seen. [12]

Thus, the purpose of this article is to analyze current educational demands and deficits of Russian teachers in the field of continuing professional education taking into account the difference in positions and professional activities.

Materials and methods

To achieve this goal, we developed a questionnaire that included the following blocks of questions with appropriate branching: blocks of questions for heads and deputy heads of educational organizations, for teachers and methodologists of educational organizations, a general block of questions on deficits of additional education in pedagogy and the areas of continuing education relevant to respondents, socio-demographic block. In the main blocks the participants were asked questions on the following topics: the tasks that help to solve the problems of training in additional vocational education programs, the criteria for selecting additional vocational education programs, expectations of learning outcomes, deficits that are felt by respondents in the field of continuing education. The questionnaire was designed in such a way that the participants saw only their own block of questions and could not influence the choice of respondents from another group.

The questionnaire was then posted on the Internet and sent to the active addresses of heads and deputy heads of educational organizations, for teachers and methodologists at educational organizations that cooperate with MCPU, and also posted on social networks. The data were statistically processed using IBM SPSS 21 software with the use of mathematical statistics methods.

The study was conducted from January 12 to 28, 2021. A total of 1,257 people took part in the survey: 917 teachers, 162 deputy heads of educational organization and heads of educational unit, 96 heads of educational organizations, 54 methodologists, 22 respondents holding other positions in educational organization or having a profession related to pedagogy (teachers-psychologists, psychologists, speech therapists, master students of educational institutions, teaching assistants, etc.), 6 people chose not to answer this question. Most of the respondents are between 41 and 51 years old (370 respondents), between 51 and 60 years old (356 respondents), between 31 and 40 years old (313 respondents). The average number of years in the position held is more than 8 years (937 respondents).

The respondents were divided into two large groups: teachers in educational organizations - 993 respondents (teachers, methodologists and other positions) and 258 (heads of educational

organizations and deputy heads of educational organizations, heads of educational units). This allowed us to conduct a comparative analysis of the main issues:

- tasks that training in additional professional education programs helps to solve,
- criteria for selecting additional vocational education programs, which provides insight into the consumer behavior of this category,
- the main requests for training on the programs of additional professional education, both from the teachers' point of view and from the point of view of the educational organization managers in relation to the employees,
- expectations from the training results of the teachers and managers of the educational organization in relation to the employees,
- deficits felt by the respondents in the field of continuing education.

Results

Thus, the main tasks, which continuing education can solve, on the part of teachers were indicated as the following: "to increase work efficiency" (502 answers) and "to improve the quality of education" (487 answers).

On the part of heads of educational organizations with regard to teachers, the following main tasks were chosen: "ensuring of education quality" and "professional development of school teachers" (148 answers each). Thus, it is evident that both teachers and managers agree in defining priority tasks to be provided by training in continuing education programs: improvement of education quality and enhancement of work efficiency.

This actualizes the task of developing practice-oriented professional development programs containing technologies, methods and tools that allow to improve the performance of learners with different educational needs in a short period of time.

Teachers identified the following criteria for selecting further professional education programs: "presentations of further education programs at meetings and events" (463 responses), "feedback from colleagues" (422 responses), "research results and opinions of specialists" (380 responses) and information letters from educational authorities (320 responses). The distribution of answers of heads of educational institutions is generally consistent with the distribution of teachers' answers: 120 respondents mentioned "presentations of continuing education programs at meetings and events" as the first criterion of programme selection, 98 - "recommendations of heads of educational authorities", 96 - "opinions or wishes of teachers", 94 - "feedback from colleagues" and 92 - "research results". This opens up new directions for the promotion of programs and clarification of marketing and communication strategies on the part of public and private educational organizations that provide continuing professional education to teachers.

The following areas of learning in continuing education programs were identified by teachers as the most important for them: "subject orientation" (630 answers) and "development of digital competencies" (557 answers), the third most popular option was "skills of working with children with disabilities" (312 answers). This demonstrates well the impact of complete distance learning on educational needs, when digital competence becomes important. Also, quite a lot of respondents noted the options "development of mentoring and project management skills" (295 responses), "psychological and pedagogical competence (development of emotional intelligence, mediation, working with conflict situations, age psychology, social psychology of small groups, etc.)" (258 responses). (258 responses) and "formation of functional literacy of students" (222 responses). Here, the influence of global trends and desire for professional development in the

field of psychological and pedagogical competence are observed in view of increased communication with parents.

Heads of educational organizations consider the main directions of training in the system of continuing education for teachers: "subject-oriented programs" (142 answers) and development of digital competencies (152 answers), as well as skills of working with children with disabilities (100 answers), which fully correlates with the teachers' answers. The preferred directions of continuing education training for head masters are: assessment of education quality (142 answers), digital transformation of education (114 answers) and legal aspects of educational organization management (78 answers).

The areas of school managers' priority choice are conditioned by the existing gap: the need for functioning of evaluation activity system (ESQA) in educational organization and absence of unified regulations for internal quality assessment system. The ESQA model is based on the institution's target benchmarks, the requirements of the FSES implementation in the conditions of school transformation, educational needs of students and their parents, strategic objectives for the development of the municipal and regional education system. Therefore, each management team should independently determine the parameters of ESQA formation, develop, implement and maintain the model. All this requires school leaders to have the skills to manage results based on the analysis of non-falsified data within the legal framework.

An important aspect for understanding the development and relevance of continuing education for teachers and heads of educational organization is the expected results after the training. For teachers, the primary results are "improved results of their work" (878 answers), "increased level of their professional skills" (772 answers) and "desire for self-realization" (342 answers). (342 answers) indicates a high level of professional motivation of teachers. Managers, on the other hand, note primarily the improvement of training quality (184 responses), increasing professional activity of teaching staff (158 responses) and implementation of pedagogical innovations (154 responses), which not only correlate with the expected results of training in the position of a teacher, but also are important for full and comprehensive development of educational organization and implementation of the main tasks set by the heads of educational organizations.

The respondents identified the following as the main deficits in the sphere of continuing education in Russia: the lack of courses in their region that would fully meet their educational needs (653 responses), insufficient information about the programs and courses (487 responses) and low quality of the course content (364 responses).

Discussion

Thus, we can conclude that, on the whole, Russian teachers and heads of educational organizations are quite strongly involved in the sphere of continuing education, although the main problem - the difficulty of meeting the needs in new methods and techniques, especially in the subject competences corresponding to new knowledge and discoveries of modern science - is still not completely solved.

Private and state educational institutions of continuing education need, first of all, to pay attention to improving the quality of the content of courses, to make them more focused on specific educational tasks and/or educational outcomes, and also to use a modern system of marketing communications using new effective tools of digital marketing (targeting mailing lists, expanding client bases, SMM tools, implementation of artificial intelligence in their system of client management, etc.)

One of such solutions is the model of an urban hub of continuing education (hereinafter referred to as a Hub of CE) developed and tested by Moscow City Pedagogical University on the basis of Russian and foreign studies [3,4,7,10,13]. A hub for CE performs the following functions:

- analyses and forecasts the market for continuing education services for a variety of target groups in the long, medium and short term;
- aggregates additional education services by attracting and using the best educational practices and technologies, forms and models of programme development and implementation;
- supports the design of individual educational routes for citizens based on the analysis of current trends, requests and preferences, as well as the results of diagnostics of existing skills, which allows choosing the training programs that meet the maximum needs of citizens;
- manages the interaction with customers, ensuring a smooth flow, movement and use of services and products of additional education, as well as a variety of resources: personnel, content, advertising and information, methodological, etc. [8]

Such innovative structures aimed at generating qualitatively new products and services in the sphere of continuing education, meeting the requirements and challenges of time and the needs of each student should become an integral part of the system of professional development of teachers and heads of Russian schools, focused on professional respect for each student and emphasizing his motivation for self-improvement and professional growth [15].

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